

JALALUDDIN MANGUBERDI" BY MAQSUD SHEIKHZODA IS A HISTORICAL-ROMANTIC TRAGEDY

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Annotation: Talented poet Maqsud Masumbek oglu Shaykhzoda was born in Azerbaijan, grew up in Uzbekistan as a creator, in the heart of Uzbeks, grew up as a famous penman, a great Uzbek writer. became a representative. The prince is also a poet, scholar, publicist, playwright and skilled translator. This article discusses Maqsud Shaykhzoda and his historical drama "Jaloliddin Manguberdi".

Keywords: word artist, philologist, scientist, poet, publicist, philosopher, " playwright, spiritual world, creative work, tradition, philosophical generalizations, passionate journalism, tragedy (tragedy), high taste, poetics, pathos.

Maqsud Ma'sumbek's son Sheikhzada is one of the word artists who made a great contribution to the development of Uzbek literature. Maqsud Shaikhzada, candidate of philological sciences, worked as an associate professor at Nizamiy Tashkent State Pedagogical Institute (now university) until the end of his life. His His passionate poetry, his scientific and critical works full of deep thoughts and generalizations, his poetic translations filled with high taste and sophistication occupy an important place in the Uzbek literature of the 20th century.

The best works of Sheikhzadeh were written in a truly modern spirit. In them, the spiritual world, heart, thoughts and desires of a person are expressed in a unique style - with journalistic enthusiasm, through original poetic images, in deep philosophical generalizations. The qualities of the poet's poetry matured thanks to

long creative work, thanks to creative learning from the experiences of Russian poets and, first of all, Mayakovsky. In the poetry of Sheikhzada, Eastern classics and the traditions of Russian poets are surprisingly intertwined. As Sheikhzadeh himself admitted, he started practicing poetry before he was literate. When talking about the work of Sheikhzadeh during the war years, it is impossible not to mention the drama "Jalaluddin Manguberdi", which tells the history of the peoples of Central Asia. This drama was written in 1944 and was staged in the Uzbek State Academic Drama Theater named after Hamza. Our academic writers Oybek and Gafur Ghulam: "For a long time, he dreams of a long-lived, artistically significant stage work. We were "Jalaluddin" is able to answer this dream," they admitted.

When we get acquainted with the content of the work, we see that Maqsud Sheikhzade's poetic and intelligent scholarly skills are fully demonstrated in it. It was not for nothing that the poet was interested in the historical theme and wrote a dramatic work during the war years. In the fight against fascism, all nations, regardless of their nationality, were greatly helped by their heroic traditions of the past and their struggles against foreign invaders. That is why literature began to turn to historical themes in order to revive these heroic traditions. That's it As a result of these views, this drama of Sheikhzada was created.

The work is written in poetic form. This method made it possible to describe the events in the play clearly and the character of the characters in an impressive and attractive way. The text of the work is read in one breath and has a deep impact on a person. The main thing is that complex scenes also reach the reader's mind. The characters of the last Khorezmshah Jalaluddin Manguberdi and the leader of the people Temur Malik, who led the fight against the Mongol invaders of the 13th century, are central in the work. The poet Sheikhzada does not show the full life of Jalaluddin, but describes his life until he was decisively defeated by the Mongols. In doing so, he was able to reveal the limitations of the hero's worldview, the rottenness of the feudal environment, and the image of the Mongol invaders.

The image of the main character of the work, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, his human appearance - honesty and purity, cruelty to the enemy, and brave character leave a great impression on both the reader and the viewer.

The work attracts one's attention with its philosophical spirit and the attractiveness of the language in the artistic image. If we dwell on the interaction between the historical truth and the artistic texture of the hero of the work in the tragedy, the author's image of the historical person and his artistic image has become lifelike. Jalaluddin Manguberdi's behavior, his words, manner of dealing are shown in harmony with the historical environment. The scenes of Jalaluddin's hateful appeal to those who betrayed the Motherland, such as his father Muhammadshah, Amir Badriddin, Yodgorbek, and his kind treatment towards his mother and sister Sultanbegim, were impressive and lifelike.

In the tragedy, the image of Jalaluddin Manguberdi is revealed more through other characters in the work. For example, in the communication with the tyrant Genghis Khan, the traitor to his country Shah Muhammad, the weak emir Badriddin, his brave, His hatred for people who are loyal to his country, conquerors and traitors is manifested as a human being. As a result, we fall in love with this patriotic, courageous, courageous, intelligent person, and we read one of the bright pages of our history in his image.

Thanks to Maqsud Shaykhzada's skills in creating a stage work, the conflicting period in which Manguberdi lived, people's lives are clearly, vividly, attractively depicted in the play, and most importantly, people are believable. In the work, the image of the great leader, the hero of our country - Jalaluddin Manguberdi is embodied in all his glory.

In short, the tragedy of "Jalaluddin Manguberdi" is a perfect stage work that tells about the most tragic period of the history of our country. The monologues of the stage heroes Jalaluddin Manguberdi and Timur Malik sound like hymns

honoring our country and people. This work is valuable as a true masterpiece of Uzbek stage culture.

"A poet is first and foremost a citizen of his country, a servant of his people. Cultivating the human spirit, increasing the elements of goodness, raising the people's sense of beauty and sophistication to a higher level is the sacred task of art. If I, along with my comrades, contributed to this sacred mission, I have the right to consider that I have not lived in vain..." the poet wrote in his memoirs. A great poet, scientist and Playwright Maqsud Shaykhzada had a short life. But he left a rich literary heritage. During the years of independence, his work was appreciated and he was awarded the Order of Merit (in 2001).

Maqsud Sheikhzada, the poet of thoughts, reached the peak of perfection, which he achieved thanks to his deep knowledge and thinking, and tireless work. The blessed name and works of the literary scholar, philosophical poet with such qualities will remain in the hearts of literature lovers for many years. The following lines sound as if spoken by the poet in his mind:

Don't say he's dead or gone, we're alive when you remember
In good and bad days, we are helpers and partners.
Our body is soil, our flower spirit is in the air
May those who remember us live longer.

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